

Spectrophotometric determination of vanadium using rhodamine-B

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Abstract : A new reagent system using rhodamine-B dye for the determination of vanadium is described. The method is based on the reaction of vanadium with acidified potassium iodide to liberate iodine. The liberated iodine bleaches the pink colour of rhodamine-B, which is measured at 553 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 2–16 µg of vanadium in final solution volume of 25 ml (0.08–0.64 ppm). The apparent molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.3 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0009 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The method is simple, sensitive and satisfactorily applied to ppm level for the determination of vanadium in different environmental and biological samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, vanadium, rhodamine-B.

Vanadium(v) is reported to be a toxic as well as an essential trace element for all living being¹. A large number of spectrophotometric method using reagents like *N*-arylhydroxamic acid², 8-hydroxyquinolene³, 3-hydroxy-2-(4)-methoxyphenyl-6-me-4*H*-chromen-4-one⁴, 4-nitrophenylhydrazine and *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine⁵ and phloroglucinol⁶ etc. have been used for the determination of vanadium. Here a new method for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium is described. The method involves liberation of iodine by the reaction of vanadium with the potassium iodide in acidic medium. The liberated iodine bleaches rhodamine-B, and the unbleached amount of rhodamine-B is measured at 553 nm. The method is simple, sensitive and has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of vanadium in polluted water, soil, leaf, steel, blood and urine samples. The results have been compared with the method where NPH and phloroglucinol had been used⁶.

Results and discussion

The proposed method is based on the combination of the two well known reaction as follows :

(i) Liberation of iodine with the reaction of vanadium in acidic potassium iodide.

(ii) I_3^- form colourless ion pair complex with rhodamine-B

The absorption spectra of rhodamine-B dye showed a maximum absorbance at 553 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the

concentration range of 2–16 µg of vanadium per 25 ml of the final solution (0.08–0.64 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.03 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0009 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

2 ml of 1% potassium iodide, 1 ml of 5 *M* hydrochloric acid and 1 ml of 0.05% rhodamine-B was sufficient for complete reaction. Constant absorbance values were obtained within the pH range 1–2 and the room temperature 25–35 °C. Time of 15–20 min was necessary for the completion of the reaction. The repeatability of the method was checked by the analysis of the working standard solution containing 9 µg vanadium per 25 ml over a period of seven days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0275 and 6.642% respectively. The effect of various foreign species on the reaction were studied by adding known amounts of these compounds to a solution containing 9 µg per 25 ml of vanadium. Most of the ions were found not to interfere under the optimum conditions employed. The tolerance limits (ppm) of different foreign ions in a solution containing 9 µg/25 ml of vanadium are given in Table 2.

Experimental

A Systronics spectrophotometer model 109 and Systronics pH meter model 331 were used for spectral and pH measurement respectively. All chemicals used were of the best available grade.

To prepare stock solution of vanadium (E. Merck) 0.4592 g of ammonium metavanadate was dissolved in

Table 1. Comparison with other spectrophotometric method

Sl. no.	Reagent	Medium pH	λ_{max} nm	Range ppm	Remarks	Ref.
1.	<i>N</i> -Phenylbenzo-hydroxamic acid	5–9 <i>M</i> HCl	510	2.4–7.8	Strong interference of various ions	2
2.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-cinnamohydroxamic acid	2.7–7.5 <i>M</i> HCl	540	1.6–7.2	Ti ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI} , interfere	2
3.	Benzohydroxamic acid	1.2–5.5 HCl	450	2.8–8.2	Fe ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Al ^{III} , interfere	2
4.	8-Hydroxyquinolene	0.7 <i>M</i> HCl	430	1.0–5.00	Extractive, Mo ^{VI} , Sn ^{II} , interfere	3
5.	3-Hydroxy-2-(4)-methoxyphenyl-6-me-4 <i>H</i> -chromen-4-one	0.12 <i>M</i> CH ₃ COOH	400	0.23–2.45	Extractive, Mo ^{VI} , Sn ^{II} , interfere	4
6.	4-NPH and <i>N</i> -(1-naphthyl-ethylenediamine)	5–8 <i>M</i> HCl	550	0.80–3.00	Oxidants and reductants interfere	5
7.	NPH and phloroglucinol	12.0–12.5 <i>M</i> NaOH	440	0.20–2.00	Less sensitive	6
8.	Present method	5 <i>M</i> HCl	553	0.08–0.64	More sensitive, less interference	

warm double distilled water. A few drops of conc. sulphuric acid and potassium permanganate were added dropwise with shaking till the appearance of light pink colour. Volume was made up to 100 ml and vanadium was determined titrimetrically using potassium permanganate⁷.

Table 2. Effect of foreign ions

Concentration of vanadium = 9 µg/25 ml		Tolerance ^a limits (ppm)
Compd.	Ions	
BaCl ₂	Ba ^{II}	3050
ZrCl ₄	Zr ^{IV}	
Na ₂ CO ₃	CO ₃ ²⁻	2050
NH ₄ Cl	NH ₄ ^I	
MnCl ₂	Mn ^{II}	1000
NiCl ₂	Ni ^{II}	
NaHPO ₄	PO ₄ ³⁻	700
Na ₂ SO ₄	SO ₄ ²⁻	
AgNO ₃	Ag ^I	350
HgCl ₂	Hg ^{II}	
BiCl ₃	Bi ^{III}	150
TiCl ₄	Ti ^{IV}	
Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	W ^{VI}	100
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	Cr ^{VI}	
FeCl ₃	Fe ^{III}	
CaCl ₂	Ca ^{II}	
NaNO ₃	NO ₃ ⁻	

^aCauses an error of ±2% in absorbance value.

A 1% (w/v) solution of potassium iodide (E. Merck) was prepared in distilled water. 0.05% (w/v) solution of rhodamine-B was prepared in distilled water. 0.1 *N* aqueous solution of potassium permanganate (Loba Chemie) and oxalic acid (A.R.) was prepared. 5 *M* aqueous solution of hydrochloric acid was prepared.

Procedure :

To an aliquot of a working standard of 2–16 µg vanadium, oxalic acid was added dropwise to destroy the excess of potassium permanganate. Then 1 ml hydrochloric acid was added followed by 2 ml of potassium iodide. The mixture was shaken gently till the appearance of a yellow colour indicating the liberation of iodine. 1 ml of rhodamine-B was added to it and shaken for few min. After 15 min the volume was made up to 25 ml by adding distilled water. The absorbance of the dye was measured at 553 nm.

Application :

The proposed method has been satisfactorily applied to the determination of vanadium in polluted water, plant materials, steel, soil and biological samples.

In polluted water : Water samples were taken from different points upstream and downstream of Shivnath river, which receives effluent from various industries. Since these samples gave negative test for vanadium, synthetic samples

were prepared by adding known amounts of vanadium. Vanadium content was then determined by the present and reported method⁶.

In soil : 1 g each of soil samples, which were found to contain negligible amount of vanadium, were spiked with known amount of vanadium. These samples were first fused with 5 g of sodium carbonate. After adding 25 ml water, it was evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water, filtered and analysed by the present and reported method⁶.

In steel : A weighed quantity of a steel sample (No. BS-94614) containing about 1 mg of vanadium was dissolved in 40% nitric acid. It was slowly evaporated to dryness and the residue was treated with 0.5 ml of hydrochloric acid. Insoluble brown yellow precipitate of hydrated tungstic acid was filtered off by Whatman filter paper no. 42. Filtrate was again evaporated to dryness followed by the addition of 0.5 ml hydrochloric acid. Process was repeated 2–3 times and the contents were diluted to 25 ml. Suitable aliquots of this solution were taken and vanadium content was determined by the proposed and reported method⁶.

In plant leaf : Dried cabbage leaf samples, each of 2 g were spiked with known amount of vanadium, digested with 0.2 g potassium sulphate and 10 ml of nitric acid for 30 min. Then 10 ml of conc. nitric acid was added and heated to dryness. For complete oxidation of leaves, the process was repeated 2–3 times. Residue was digested on a water-bath for 30 min after adding 25 ml of 1 : 3 dil. nitric acid to hydrolyse polyphosphate to orthophosphate. The contents were again evaporated to dryness and the residual matter was extracted with hot distilled water, which was then filtered and cooled. Vanadium was then determined by the proposed and reported method⁶.

In blood : 5 ml deproteinised human blood samples were spiked with known quantity of vanadium. These were treated with ~5 g potassium sulphate and 5 ml nitric acid and heated to dryness. The process was repeated 2–3 times.

Residue was dissolved in 25 ml of 1 : 3 nitric acid and kept on water bath for digestion. It was again evaporated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in distilled water, filtered, cooled and analysed⁸.

In urine : Deproteinised urine samples each of 50 ml were concentrated upto ~5 ml and treated as described above. Vanadium content was then analysed by the reported⁶ and present method.

Conclusion :

The present method for the determination of vanadium is rapid, simple, selective and sensitive. This method has been compared with other spectrophotometric method reported for vanadium.

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